

EELISA

European University

**EELISA INNOCORE EELISA MULTI LABS (SHARING FACILITIES
& EQUIPMENT)**

**Deliverable 4.3 - Definition of the main features of the IT
booking system**

Date: 17/02/2023

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V	Date	WP Leader	Reviewed by:
1	20/01/2023	PSL	PSL (Antoine Mercier & Ilaria Ciofini)
2	14/02/2023	PSL	FAU quality check (David SCHKADE)
3	30/01/2023	PSL	EELISA InnoCORE quality assurance coordinator (Juan Manuel Munuoz)

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This deliverable is the result of the work made in WP4 *EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)*.

The objective of the task was to define the features of a booking system of facilities that will help researchers to get to know the landscape of available facilities in EELISA and to get in touch with their colleagues.

By enabling those collaborations, we aim at creating more sustainable links between researchers thus making EELISA InnoCORE a reality for them.

This document will serve as the basis for developing the terms of reference for a subcontract managed by PSL (via its school Chimie ParisTech PSL) for this IT support. Before issuing the tender, consistency checks will be made to ensure the tool will be compatible with the current EELISA community platform developed at FAU.

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Responsibles for WP4

Partner	Acronym	Contact person for WP4
Universidad Politecnica De Madrid	UPM	Mrs Lidia CEREZO, TTO contact point for scientific and technological services and indicators
Ecole Nationale Des Ponts Et Chaussees	ENPC	Mr. Emmanuel GIRARD, Deputy director of Research Department & Mr. Mustafa SEVIMLI Project Manager
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nuernberg	FAU	Mr. David SCHKADE, Strategic Projects Department
Istanbul Teknik Universitesi	ITÜ	Mr. Ömer ŞAHIN, Professor
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Mr Pasqualantonio PINGUE, Head of Research & Innovation AREA and CCO at NEST Laboratory
Scuola Superiore Di Studi Universitari E Di Perfezionamento S Anna	SSSA	Mrs. Rossella RASO, Project Manager
Universitatea Politehnica Din Bucuresti	UPB	Mr Catalin NEGRU, Senior Researcher
Budapesti Muszaki Es Gazdasagtudományi Egyetem	BME	Mr. László LENGYEL, Director of Center for University-Industry Cooperation
Universite Paris Sciences et Lettres	PSL	Mrs. Ilaria CIOFINI, VP Research @ Chimie ParisTech PSL

Review and quality check by EELISA

In order to guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the document has been sent to the EELISA Office.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

Research Infrastructures. The term “Research infrastructures” includes any piece of equipment that might be available to ‘customer’ whether they are in a laboratory (commercial device or developed/customed by researchers themselves), on a platform.

Research Structures. The term “Research Structures” includes the research centres, research hubs, research groups and research labs, institutes with a research focus, which produce significant research outcomes and thereby, represent a R&I capacity.

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 44 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a collective strategic research area and research infrastructure map (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 Rationale and purposes of the “booking system”

The work on the survey among researchers and research managers to ask them to be included in an EELISA catalogue to give more visibility to their equipment or facilities (D4.1 - Mapping of existing facilities) was planned as a first step to initiate new collaborations.

Nevertheless, a sole catalogue is not sufficient to enable collaboration. Two additional pieces of work were needed: 1) defining common rules for sharing equipment that led to a separate deliverable (4.2 - Agreement on the main consensual rules of access to open facilities) and 2) enabling research to contact and “book” the equipment. Without this IT tool, it has been considered that the impact of the catalogue would be very low for EELISA researchers.

The main outcome of this work is to increase bottom-up collaborations (involving researchers and/or students) that could be measured by the number of mobilities within EELISA and bring additional visibility to research teams hosting those pieces of equipment.

3 Description and list of requirements

3.1 From a booking system to a contact making system

Following discussions held in WP4, it turned out that the “booking system” should be closer to an enhanced catalogue to initiate contact rather than being a real “booking system”. Indeed, participation in the survey to build the catalogue revealed that the diversity of situations is very large: some partners do have well established platforms or on-line catalogues and others do not. Most often, a researcher designing his/her piece of equipment suffers from relatively low visibility and does not have access to tools to manage bookings or even contacts. At UPM or SNS, there is a standard form to formalize the collaboration but there is no tool to facilitate the very first contact before making it official via a collaboration agreement.

In addition, the possibility that anyone in EELISA may be in a position to book a slot for a facility might create difficulties in managing those facilities (too many solicitations, priority settings not well defined, etc.) and diminish the positive impact of EELISA. Besides, we also found in the survey that most of the facilities are already close to full capacity so their openness will be limited.

That is why it has been agreed that the booking system will be an IT support to enable researchers to get in touch with each other and to discuss possibilities of collaboration rather than a direct booking system.

3.2 Requirements

This IT system will be a module of the EELISA website. In such a way, the existing facilities in EELISA will be clearly visible to the researchers of all institutions.

3.2.1 Phase one – visibility and contacting

During this phase it is expected that researchers contact their local officer to be included in the catalogue and fill in a dedicated form. The focus of this phase is to provide greater visibility and enabling contact.

The display of the entries will rely on the existing catalogue and will look like the following:

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<p>Equipment for extracellular electrophysiology EELISA Research Areas Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences</p>	<p>Description Technique for recording the electrical activity of cell cultures with high temporal and spatial resolution. Extracellular electrophysiology service using the Multichannel Systems MEA 2100 microelectrode array system.</p> <p>Type.....: A single or several equipment Activities.....: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities Load.....: More information: More information available on this website: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-electrofisiologia-extracelular/</p> <p>Location Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology</p> <p>Contact person Gustavo Víctor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB ⇒ Link to the contact form</p> <p>Way(s) of collaboration Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-electrofisiologia-extracelular/</p>
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<p>Chemical and analytical methodologies EELISA Research Areas Health - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences</p>	<p>Description The SEISAD team develops different chemical and analytical methodologies and tools aiming to propose valuable insights in clinical and environmental diagnostics and therapy. The main equipment and facilities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capillary Electrophoresis coupled to UV-visible, fluorescence or mass spectrometry detectors • Flow Chemistry • 3D printing for microfabrication • Miniaturised devices • Optical Fluorescence Microscopes • Potentiostats • Scanning electrochemical microscope <p>This is a commercial product.</p> <p>Type.....: A single or several equipment Activities.....: Research activities Load.....: Almost fully used More information: More information available on this website: https://iclehs.fr/research/seisad/</p> <p>Location Université PSL (PSL), Institute of Chemistry for Life and Health Sciences (i-CLeHS)</p> <p>Contact person Laura TRAPIELLA ALFONSO, Assistant Professor - Institute of Chemistry for Life and Health Sciences (i-CLeHS) ⇒ Link to the contact form</p> <p>Way(s) of collaboration Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level) - For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)</p>
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The system will create a unique link to a contact form that the researcher can use to start an e-mail exchange about a possible visit. From the existing contact form (Annex 1 – Current contact form), item 1 (*Select the facility you wish to visit*) will be automatically populated.

By doing so, there is minimum exposure of email addresses on the web and the system can record and report contacting.

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3.2.2 Phase two – consolidation and connections

In phase two, application programming interfaces (APIs) will be developed to enable automatic retrieval of equipment from existing local systems. To date UPM's catalogue is available here: <https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/>

Furthermore, it will be possible for any EELISA researcher to add a new entry directly on the catalogue with the implementation of a validation process to be agreed beforehand by all EELISA partners.

The link to the form for new entries to the catalogue will be integrated into the system while having a redirection mechanism for those EELISA members who already have a local system. This way, a researcher will not have to enter the data twice, and there will be no need for a manual central feed into the database.

4 Conclusion

In such a way, the existing facilities in EELISA will be clearly visible to the researchers of all EELISA institutions. The administrative burdens will be as low as possible for researchers taking benefit from local implementation of existing catalogue. It is expected that it will boost existing or new collaborations proving a wide range of opportunities and a clear idea of the access rules and processes.

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Annex 1 – Current contact form

Reservation tool for the EELISA facilities

This reservation tool automatically posts a request to the scientific manager of the facility. The acceptance of the request and all further exchange are under the full responsibility of the scientific manager. Posting a request does not automatically imply its acceptance. The full list and description of the EELISA open facilities can be found at *[url of the catalogue]*.

Identify yourself

First Name

Last Name

Position

Are you part of one of the EELISA member?

- Yes
- No

For those who select yes:

Select your host institution:

- Technical University of Madrid (UPM)
- Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)
- Ecoles des Ponts ParisTech (ENPC)
- Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU)
- Istanbul Technical University (ITU)
- Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS)
- Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (SSSA)
- Politehnica University of Bucharest (UPB)
- Université PSL (PSL)

Laboratory/Institute:

[Here will be a scrolling menu of all EELISA research structures with an additional field 'other' allowing to insert structures that are not yet in our list or simply a field allowing to write the laboratory name.]

E-mail address:

(Please enter a valid e-mail address. It will be used for all further correspondence with the facility manager.)

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For those who select no:

Please provide full details of your institution:

Name in English

Address

Country

Type:

- Academic
- Non-Academic

E-mail address:

(Please enter a valid e-mail address. It will be used for all further correspondence with the facility manager.)

Identify the facility and clarify the scientific objects

1. Select the facility you wish to visit:

The full list and description of the EELISA open facilities can be found at [url of the catalogue]

Reference of the facilities from the catalogue:

2. Specify the period you would prefer for the visit

From

To

3. Provide a brief description of the scientific aim of the visit.

Please clearly identify the devices you would like to access and the work planned [max 3000 characters, excluding spaces]!

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4. Any relevant additional scientific information can be uploaded here:

[field allowing pdf only upload]

[Send the request](#)

GDPR compliance box

2 buttons: Send / Cancel

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